

WEB ILOVALAR DASTURIY TAMINOTINI YARATISH

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda Internetning ommaviyligi haqida gapirish o'rinsiz. Internet hayotimizning bir bo'lagiga aylandi, biz uning xizmatlaridan har kuni foydalanishga odatlandik. Hozirda ixtiyoriy inson web-texnologiyalarning inson hayotining ta'lim, kommersiya, siyosat, ko'ngil ochar, bo'laklariga kirib borganligini tasavvur eta oladi va uning guvohi va foydalanuvchisiga aylanmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: web-texnologiyalar, Plug-in dasturlar, Web sahifalar, Web sahifalar, XHTML, XML, HTML.

Abstract: It is inappropriate to talk about the popularity of the Internet today. The Internet has become a part of our lives, we have become accustomed to using its services every day. Nowadays, any volunteer can imagine that web technologies have penetrated the educational, commercial, political, entertainment parts of human life and are becoming its witness and user.

Keywords: web-technologies, Plug-in programs, Web pages, Web pages, XHTML, XML, HTML.

Internet turli xil insonlarni yagona maqsad bilan birlashishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Hamma Internet tarmog'idan biror turdagi axborot olishga harakat qiladi. Shunday vaqtlar keladiki, hujjatni Internetda chop etish malakasi yozuv mashinasidan foydalanish kabi har bir, hatto o'rta ma'lumotga ega bo'lgan insonning qo'lidan keladi.

Mazkur maqolada web-hujjatlarni yaratish, ularni Internetda chop etish, web-hujjatni ko'rkamlashtirish, qiziqarli va o'ziga tortuvchi qilib yaratish, vaqti kelsa ma'lumotlarmi yangilash kabi vazifalarni o'rgatishga mo'ljallangan.

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Dastlabki web-sahifalar juda sodda tuzilishga ega bo'lib, ular matnni formatlash va giperko'rsatkichlardan tarkib topgan edi. Web texnologiyalar rivojlanishi natijasida Web sahifalar tarkibida Plug-in dasturlar joylashtirila boshlandi, natijada Web sahifalarga inter faol xususiyati berildi. Web texnologiyalarning rivojlanishining oxirgi natijalaridan biri bu skript tillaridir (Script Languages). Ularni ishlatishdan maqsad Web serverining ishini engillashtirish, xar-xil ishlar uchun Web serverini bezovta qilmasdan, bunday masalalarni foydalanuvchi

kompyuterining o'zida yaratishdir. Web texnologiyasining oxirgi erishgan yutuqlaridan biri dinamik Web sahifalardir. Dinamik Web sahifalar CGI dasturlar bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lib, CGI dasturlar serverda joylashgan va server imkoniyatlarini ishlatuvchi dasturlardir. Ular serverga kelgan so'rovlarni qayta ishlaydi va qayta ishlash natijasida yangi Web sahifa hosil bo'ladi.

Kompyuterlarni tarmoqqa ulash g'oyalari birinchi bo'lib, 1960-yillarning boshlarida paydo bo'la boshladi. 1965 yili Lourens Roberts va Tomas Merrvill Kaliforniya va Massachusetts shtatlarida joylashgan ikki kompyuterni bir-biriga bog'lashdi. Bog'lanish telefon yo'llari orqali amalga oshirilib, dunyo tarixida birinchi kompyuter tarmog'i bo'ldi. Bu texnologiya bilan AQSH Mudofaa Vazirligining DARPA agentligi qiziqib, ularga harbiy qo'shinlarni bir tarmoqqa birlashtirish g'oyasi yoqib qoldi. Agentlik mutaxassislari bu g'oya bo'yicha qattiq ishlar olibborib, 1969-yili ARPANET tarmog'ini yaratishdi.

1971-yil oktabr oyida insoniyat tarixida ilk marotaba BBN kompaniyasi xodimi Ray Tomlinson elektron pochta orqali xabar yubordi. Matn klaviaturaning yuqori qatoridagi QWERTYUIOP harflardan iborat bo'lib, Tomlinsonning o'ziga yuborilgan. 1972-yilning mart oyida Tomlinson SNGMSG va READMAIL elektron xabarlarini yuborish va o'qish dasturlarini yaratdi. O'sha paytning o'zida ARPANET ning barcha foydalanuvchilariga yuborilgan xatda elektron manzillarning @ yordamida tuzilish asoslarini bildirdi (login_name@host_name).

1974-yili tarmoq rivojlanish tarixida TCP/IP(transmission control protokol/internet protokol) tarmoqlararo protokol ishlab chiqarilishi natijasida keskin yuksalish sodir bo'ldi. Bu kashfiyotning mualliflari Robert Kan va Stenford universitetining professori Vinton Serf.

Bu vaqtda TCP/IP ma'lumotni paketga bo'lib uzatish protokoli joriy qilinishi boshlandi. Bu protokol hozirda ham asosiy protokol bo'lib qo'llanib kelmoqda.

Bu kashfiyotdan avval tarmoqdagi ma'lumotlar faqat matn ko'rinishida uzatilar edi. Berners-Li va uning hamkasblari WWW nomi bilan mashhur texnologiyani yaratishdi. Bu texnologiya rang-barang web sahifalarni yaratishga yo'l ochib, giperko'rsatkichlar yordamida Internetda boshqa sahifalar bilan bog'lashga imkoniyat yaratdi. 1993-yili Mark Andrisen (Marc Andreesen) Illinois shtati universitetida Mosaic nomli web-sahifalarini ko'rish dasturini yaratdi.

1995-yili AQSH ning bir necha yillar davomida Internetni qo'llab-quvvatlab kelayotgan "Milliy fan jamg'armasi moliyaviy sarfini to'xtatdi va bundan keyin Internet mustaqil bo'lib, hech kimga qaram bo'lmay qoldi.

Web-sahifa, Web-sayt, Web-server

- Web-tehnologiya
- Web-sayt
- Web-server
- Web-sahifa

Web-sahifa - o'zining unikal adresiga ega bo'lgan va maxsus ko'rish dasturi yordamida (brauzer) ko'riluvchi hujjatdir. Unga matn, grafika, ovoz, video yoki animatsiya ma'lumotlar birlashmasi - multimediyali hujjatlar, boshqa hujjatlarga gipermurojaatlar kirishi mumkin.

Web-sayt - bir qancha web-sahifalarning mantiqiy birlashmasi.

Web-server - tarmoqqa ulangan kompyuter yoki undagi dastur hisoblanib, umumiy resurslarni klientga taqdim etish yoki ularni boshqarish vazifalarini bajaradi. Internet tarmog'ini foydalanuvchilarga tarmoq resurslaridan erkin foydalanish imkoniyatini beradigan web- serverlarsiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Bunday serverlarda Internetda taqdim etilgan axborotning katta qismi jamlangan.

Internet tarmog'ining ishlash prinsipi TCP/IP (Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol - ma'lumotlarni uzatish qaydnomasi/ Internet qaydnomasi) kompyuter tarmog'ida ma'lumotlarni uzatish qaydnomalari majmuining nomidir.

TCP (Transmission Control Protocol). Qabul qiluvchi va uzatuvchi kompyuterlarning mantiqiy bog'lanishga asoslangan ma'lumotlar uzatishini qo'llab - quvvatlovchi qaydnoma.

IP (Internet Protocol)- Ma'lumotlar uzatishni ta'minlaydi

Biz Internet tarmog'idagi Web-sahifalarni ko'rishimiz uchun WWW (WorldWide Web) deb ataluvchi servisdan foydalanamiz.

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World Wide Web (WWW, Butun dunyo o'rgimchak to'ri) - bu klient-server texnologiyasi asosida tashkil etilgan, keng tarqalgan Internet xizmatidir.

WWW (World Wide Web) - bu qanaqadir Internetdan ajratilgan ma'lum bir joy emas, kompyuter aloqa o'rnatadigan biror nima ham emas. Butunjahon o'rgimchak to'rini Internet doirasidagi xizmat deyish to'g'riroq. Web-serverlar deb ataluvchi ma'lum protokollardan, kompyuterlardan foydalanish orqali (chunki ular tarmoqqa ulangan va server dasturiy ta'minotiga ega) Internet xizmati yo'lga qo'yiladi.

Kompyuter web-server bo'lishi uchun Internetga ulangan va server dasturiy ta'minoti (DT) ga ega bo'lishi etarli. Bu DT bilan Windows, Mac OS, Unix kabi

operatsion sistemalar ta'minlay oladi. Web-server har doim Internetda "o'tiradi" va talab qilingan tomonga kerakli informatsiyani jo'natadi.

Xosting va domen tushunchalari

Web sayt yaratish bosqichlari

Web sayt yaratish usullari

Web-texnologiya klassifikatsiyasi.

Razmetkali tillar: HTML, XML, XHTML, WML.

Web-texnologiyaning (Internet-texnologiya) Web-dizayn qismini o'rganishni razmetkali til tasnifi bilan boshlaymiz.

Maxsus til mavjud bo'lib, bu til yordamida matnlar, grafik ma'lumotlar Web-sahifa hujjatga joylashtiriladi va bu hujjatni barcha kompyuterda ko'rish imkoniyati mavjuddir. Bunday maxsus tillar razmetkali tillar deb ataladi

1. Razmetkali tillar
2. XHTML
3. XML
4. HTML
5. URL da qo'llaniladigan protokollar ro'yxati:

Protokol nomi Protokol nimaga dostup berishi mumkinligi

- http:// • HTTP (web) serverlariga
- https:// • Shifrlangan ba'zi bir HTTP (web)serverlarga
- file:// • Foydalanuvchi qattiq diskidagi fayllarga
- ftp:// • FTP server fayllariga
- gopher:// • Gopher menyu va fayllariga
- news:// • Usenet yangiliklar serverlari gruppasiga
- news: • Aniq Usenet yangiliklar gruppasiga
- mailto: • Aniq elektron pochta adresiga
- telnet: • Telnet udalen serveriga

Ssenariyli tillar. "Klient-server" texnologiyasi *Klient tomonidagi ssenariylar* foydalanuvchi tomonidan kiritilayotgan ma'lumotlarni to'g'riligini serverga murojaat qilmasdan tekshiradi. Ko'p hollarda bu ssenariylar JavaScript va VBScript tillarida yoziladi.

Server tomonida bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan ssenariylar odatda sayt papkasining ichidagi maxsus papkaga joylashtiriladi. Foydalanuvchi so'roviga asosan server bu ssenariyni bajaradi. Bajarilgan ssenariy natijasi web-serverga uzatiladi va

undan so'ng klientga uzatiladi. Server tomonidagi ssenariylarni tashkil etish uchun odatda Perl, ASP, PHP, JSP va SSI kabi til va texnologiyalardan foydalaniladi.

1. Web-dasturlash texnologiyalarini
2. server tomonidagi dasturlash
3. klient tomonidagi

dasturlashXulosa

Bugungi kunda hayotimizning har bir sohasida internet texnologiyalaridan foydalanmoqdamiz. Internet turli xil insonlarni yagona maqsad bilan birlashishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Internet texnologiyalarining muhim elementlaridan biri bo'lgan web- texnologiyalar ham taraqqiy etib boryapdi. Hozirda ixtiyoriy inson web- texnologiyalarning inson hayotining ta'lim, kommersiya, siyosat, ko'ngil ochar, bo'laklariga kirib borganligini tasavvur eta oladi va uning guvohi va foydalanuvchisiga aylanmoqda. Web-dasturlash fani asosida turli dasturlash tillari yordamida web-saytlar yaratish mumkin. Har bir dasturlash tilining o'ziga hos afzallik va kamchiliklari bor. Ushbu qo'llanmada ularni farqli tomonlarini ko'rib o'tdik.

Web sahifa Internet tarmoqlarida joylashgan fayllar to'plami bo'lib, ularni soni soat sayin ko'payib bormoqda. Bu fayllarda ma'lumotlarni turli xillarini: matn, grafik, tasvir, video, audio ma'lumotlarni uchratish mumkin. Bugungi kunda Web Internet resurslari ichida eng ommaviysi hisoblanadi. Chunki, avvaldan tayyorlangan Web sahifa orqali tegishli ma'lumotlarni to'ldirish foydalanuvchining qanchadan- qancha vaqtini tejash imkonini beradi. Shu bois matematika va informatika yo'nalishida tahsil oluvchi talabalarga Web texnologiyalarni alohida kurs sifatida o'qitila boshlandi.

Bu fanni o'zlashtirishga bo'lgan chuqur intilish kelajakda yaratilajak zamonaviy ahborot texnologiyalarini saviyasini ko'tarishi shubhasiz.

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